

VALIDATION OF WIRELESS REAL-TIME MULTI-VITALS MONITORING SOLUTION FOR UTILITY IN REMOTE PATIENT MONITORING AT CLINICAL CARE PRACTICE

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Background: Recently the combination of telehealth with remote patient monitoring has paved the way for enhanced and augmented healthcare services. Its benefits include obtaining efficient, cost and time-saving patient's information and minimizing error factors. The validation of multi-vital artificial intelligence-based software (Vigo platform) was conducted to correlate the reproducibility of real-time vital recording solution internally by comparing with standard methods and externally on screen of app, nursing station and command centre.

Methods: IEC approval and informed consent were obtained. A total of seventeen healthy volunteers were admitted and deployed on the multi-vital monitoring solution kit in an ambient environmental settings and recordings continued for 24 hours. The values were correlated by those obtained through standard methods and CE-certified medical devices over the time-points 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 24 hours. ECG were measured at 0, 4, 8, 12, and 24 hours respectively.

Results: All the volunteers were male of mean age 21 ± 3 years and mean BMI 22.9 ± 1.7 Kg/m². Vital parameters included heart rate, pulse rate, respiratory rate, temperature, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure and ECG values including P-wave, PR-interval, QRS-complex, RR-interval, QT-interval, ST-Segment, T-wave were strongly and significantly correlated internally ranging 88-98% ($p > 0.01$) and 100% correlated externally ($p > 0.01$).

Conclusion: All the vital parameters and ECG measures were strongly matched and correlated internally and externally. This work supports remote monitoring technology as part of remote patient care. Thus, the software solution Vigo platform that was developed in this work may become a route to patients' safety.

Keywords: Remote monitoring, multi-vitals, telehealth, artificial intelligence, wireless wearable, patch biosensors

1. Introduction:

Vitals are essential biological signals that reflect the ongoing physio-pathological condition of the body. Temperature, heart rate (HR), pulse rate (PR), respiratory rate (RR), oxygen saturation (SpO₂), and blood pressure (BP) are the cardinal vital signs that form the paramount basis for any diagnosis(1). Vital monitoring in patients has developed from manual evaluation methods to the

utilization of automatic devices like electronic blood pressure instruments and glucometer kits. However, vitals monitoring is a manpower-intensive activity and even advanced countries with high-grade medical infrastructure are also facing the problem of optimizing the use of infrastructure to improve the better patient care(2). The periodicity, accuracy, vital chart formats, patient load, and nurse attitude towards patient care are determined as the most important parameters in providing better health care.

The concept of mobile health was introduced by Robert Istepanian in the late 1960s. Since then Telehealth, Remote patient monitoring's were initiated by utilizing mobile communication network technologies and subsequently Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) programs have been merged with health care(3,4). The integration of AI and ML algorithms in cloud services are making every effort for continuous mobile, remote healthcare services. This leverage the clinician to access de-compensated patients' status at each moment and make a timely decision on the treatment process with seamless data(5).

During COVID-19 pandemic RPM has gained a lot of confidence worldwide and has significant advantages over traditional treatment procedures (6,7). The RPM equipped with advanced software systems such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and AI would be more beneficial for the real-time assessment of the patient's condition and to deciding the treatment procedure based on the patient's health data(8). There is a scope for the technology that will capture accurate data and serve with continuous vital signs data analysis. The technology with an early warning score mechanism, patient and healthcare provider adaptability would be of great advantage.

While wireless remote patient monitoring technologies are becoming more accessible and practical, there is a lack of publicly - available research and systematic evidence to support their use. The present validation study was planned to evaluate the Internet of Things (IoT) based Remote Multi-Vital Monitoring solution together with the lead-2 electrocardiogram (ECG) in healthy human volunteers. The MVM vitals recordings and ECG measures were correlated with standard techniques across multiple software interfaces internally as well as externally.

2. Material and Methods:

The Multi vital monitoring solution comes with smart, portable, rechargeable, and reusable devices such as Chest Biosensor (CE Number 2797), Pulse Oximeter (CE number 93/42/EEC), Armpit BP cuff (Meet ISO 81060-2:2013) and Axillary Temperature Biosensors (CE number 0086) which measures multiple vitals in real-time using the software. Vigo, a Health Tech company has devised with a platform framework that connects biosensor devices to the Vigo-Engine software for data analysis (ISO 13485:2016 and Medical Device Single Audit Program). All the devices use for integration into the Vigo Platform (Scanea) are CE Marked and FDA Approved devices. Devices include a pulse oximeter for PR and SpO₂, a single lead Electrocardiogram (ECG) biosensor for Lead-2 ECG, HR, and RR, a temperature biosensor, and an ambulatory blood pressure monitor for BP, Summarized in Table 1. The MVM Model consists of three software components: a central monitoring system (CMS) for device integration, a Bedside monitor with a vigo application in it (BSM) for patient Registration and to capture the

data, a nursing portal, and doctors app for RPM(9,10). The advantage of integrating the sensor with the software is that allows for continuous and remote monitoring.

Table 1: List of biosensors and vital parameters

S. No	Biosensor	Vital Parameter
1	Chest Biosensor	ECG Heart Rate (HR) Respiratory Rate (RR)
2	Armfit BP	Blood Pressure (BP)
3	Temperature Biosensor	Axillary Temperature
4	Wrist Pulse Oximeter	Spo2 Pulse Rate

Other Features of the Vigo Scanea Platform: The measuring times for BP can be customized. The graphs are automatically plotted, and the data is available in real time to the nurse and doctor or investigators and research personnel *via* a dedicated portal and App respectively. Historic vitals graphs would be more beneficial in assessing the trend of vital signs of patient's or participants health and well-being. The goal would be served by using real-time data measurements, evaluation, and early warning mechanisms. The Schematic is depicted in Fig 1.

Remote Patient Multivital Monitoring - Solution Overview

Fig 1: The schematic diagram -Vigo Vitals

Study Procedure: This study was designed as a prospective validation study conducted in seventeen healthy human volunteers for a period of 24 hours. The participants included were healthy adult males aged between 18-45 years, with basal metabolic index (BMI) 18.5- 25 kg/m² of normal health as determined by medical history and physical examination and lab values (Complete blood picture, renal function test, liver function test, complete urine examination, fasting blood sugar, serum electrolytes, viral markers- HIV, HBsAg, HCV, chest X-ray and ECG) within normal limits or considered insignificant by physician or investigator and agreed to comply with all study procedures. Exclusion criteria were history of contact dermatitis, skin infections or observed hypersensitivity to patch materials. Regular smoker, alcoholic and has difficulty abstaining from smoking, drinking alcohol for 48 hours before study. Participants with clinically significant physical disabilities and participants who were positive for COVID-19 RT-PCR test 24 hours prior to the study were disqualified from participation.

The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee (EC No: ESICMC/SNR/IEC-F424/02-2022) and registered with a clinical trial registry (CTRI/2022/04/041712) prior to the study. The eligible subjects were explained about the study procedure and written informed consent for screening and participation were obtained separately from all the subjects. The standard monitoring methods selected was manual with CE marked devices in case of HR, PR and RR; glass thermometer for temperature, mercury sphygmomanometer for BP, and lead 2 recorded from 12 lead ECG machine for ECG at precisely matched time points.

Fig 2: Monitoring the participant with wireless remote multivital monitoring technology-Vigo Vitals.

All the participants were in-housed at study site for 36 hours. They were instructed to report at study site 12 hours before the initiation of study. Subjects were deployed on the MVM solution in a controlled environment and continued for 24 hours. The volunteer deployed on the MVM kit is shown in Fig 2. The vitals and ECG were measured by the standard methods periodically at

intervals of 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 24 hours respectively. ECG was recorded on 12 lead ECG machine at 0, 4, 8, 12, 24 hours respectively. The breakfast, lunch and dinner were provided after 2, 6, 10-hour readings respectively. Any adverse events like rashes on the skin reported by the participants were recorded during the total in-house period. The MVM monitoring was disconnected after taking the last reading at 24 hours and participants were discharged from the study site after confirming all the vitals were stable.

2.1 The Vigo Scaena Platform Working Model

Real time vitals monitoring using wireless biosensors integrated IoT based patients monitoring platform which is called as Scaena on which multiple services were build. Scaena is a classic Io(M)T (Internet of Medical Things) platform that enables multiple end points from Android and iOS eco system. These end points connect to various CE /FDA approved biosensors to collect patient vitals. The collected vitals are streamed continuously to the Vigo Engine at the backend running on Amazon Web Services (AWS) cloud.

Fig 3: Vigo Scaena Platform: with multiple solutions

Vigo Inference engine interprets the vitals and makes them available for care providers to make decisions such as

1. Present vitals like HR, RR, SPO2, PR, Axillary Temperature, BP, and ECG as it is to the care givers.
2. Present interpretations like early warning scores (EWS) to care givers by utilising various algorithms.
3. User internally built or FDA approved third party AI engines for data interpretations.

Platform is designed to be device agnostic which means that the platform's core inference engine does not depend on the specific device or a vital is collected. Perhaps it enables to open for multiple bio-sensors available in the market for integration.

Fig 5: The monitoring software packages and validation.

The vigo platform certified with ISO 13485:2016 and medical device single audit program (MDSAP) for quality management systems and data protection 27001.

All the devices integrated into Vigo Scanea platform were CE/FDA approved devices. The data will be captured and stored in IoT Platform cloud. For ECG-report generation and interpretation Cardiologs AI will be used. The AI engine is certified by US-FDA with Regulation Number: 21 CFR 870.1425.

EWS Scoring: The data will be analyzed by real time IoT Vigo Engine and the Early warning score was employed based on the deviations in the patients' vitals trends. The EWS scoring was formulated as in table 2. The vital values with in the below mentioned normal values are represented as green and progression of the vital trends deviation from the normal are represented as yellow. The complete deviation from the normal values is represented the deterioration of the patients and it shown in red color as an indication in the monitors display.

Table 2: Normal range of vitals for EWS scoring mechanism.

Parameter	Normal Range
Heart Rate	60BPM-100BPM
PR	60BPM-100BPM
Spo2	95%-100%
Temperature	97 °F-99 °F
RR	16 BPM-18 BPM
SBP	110mmHg-130mmHg
DBP	70mmHg-90mmHg

Internal validation was defined as the correlation of the values measured by standard CE approved devices and those reflected by digital equipment integrated in the Vigo Scanea platform on the tab at bed site. The correlation of the values on the tab with those on the remote screen at nursing station, command center (CMS) and doctor app were described as external validation.

Statistical analysis: Demographic data was expressed as mean \pm SD. The data distribution was found to be non-normal and Spearman correlation analysis was performed for the assessment of external and internal validity of Multi Vital Monitoring -Vigo Vitals solution. The power of the study 90% and confidence interval more than 95% was considered as significance. All the statistical analysis was performed using the IBM SPSS version 20 software developed by Norman H. Me in 2011 at Chicago.

3. Results:

In this study a total of twenty healthy volunteers were screened out of which seventeen volunteers participated as three volunteers were failed to report at study site. All the seventeen volunteers were male of mean age 21 ± 3 years and mean BMI 22.9 ± 1.7 .

Table-1 Demographic details

Subjects	Age (Years)	Height (cm)	Weight (Kg)	BMI(Kg/m ²)
17	21 ± 3	171 ± 7	68 ± 6	22.9 ± 1.7

Correlation between Heart Rate through standard method (Control) and MVM solution (Test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants (n=17) at all 8 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.98 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 1.00 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 6

Correlation between Pulse Rate through standard method (Control) and MVM solution (Test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants (n=17) at all 8 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.98 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 1.00 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 6

Correlation between Respiratory Rate through standard method (Control) and MVM solution (Test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants (n=17) at all 8 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.89 ($p_1=0.01$) was

observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 1.00 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 6

Correlation between Temperature through standard method (Control) and MVM solution (Test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants ($n=17$) at all 8 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.73 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 1.00 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 6

Correlation between Systolic and Diastolic Blood Pressure through standard method (Control) and MVM solution (Test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants ($n=17$) at all 8 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.92 ($p_1=0.01$) for SBP and ρ_1 (rho) of 0.85 ($p_1=0.01$) for DBP respectively were observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 1.00 ($p_2=0.01$) for SBP and ρ_2 (rho) of 1.00 ($p_2=0.01$) for DBP were respectively observed. Scattered plots are shown in Figure 6

Table 3 Average ρ -values of MVM and versus CE Approved Standard Devices

Parameter	ρ (Rho) value-1 (Internal)	P- value-1	ρ value-2 External	P-value-2
Heart rate	0.98	0.01	1.00	0.01
Pulse rate	0.98	0.01	1.00	0.01
Respiratory rate	0.88	0.01	1.00	0.01
Temperature	0.74	0.01	1.00	0.01
SBP	0.92	0.01	1.00	0.01
DBP	0.85	0.01	1.00	0.01

ρ (rho): Spearman correlation coefficient

Correlation between P-wave through standard method (control) and MVM solution (test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants ($n=17$) at all 5 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.86 ($p_1=0.01$) was

observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 0.1 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 6

Correlation between PR-interval through standard method (control) and MVM solution (test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants ($n=17$) at all 5 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.86 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 0.1 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 6

Correlation between QRS-Complex through standard method (control) and MVM solution-Vigo Vitals (test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants ($n=17$) at all 5 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.87 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 0.1 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 7

Correlation between RR-interval through standard method (control) and MVM solution (test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants ($n=17$) at all 4 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.90 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 0.1 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 7

Correlation between QT-interval through standard method (control) and MVM solution (test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants ($n=17$) at all 4 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.86 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 0.1 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 7

Correlation between ST- Segment through standard method (control) and MVM solution (test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants ($n=17$) at all 4 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.86 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 0.1 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 7

Correlation between PR-interval through standard method (control) and MVM solution (test)

There was a strong correlation between control and test methods for all the participants (n=17) at all 4 time points. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_1 (rho) of 0.84 ($p_1=0.01$) was observed. The mean spearman correlation coefficient ρ_2 (rho) of 0.1 ($p_2=0.01$) was observed. Scattered plot is shown in Figure 7

Table 4: Average ρ -values of MVM ECG parameters versus Lead-2 of twelve Leads Methods

ECG Measures	ρ -value-1 Conventional Holetr	P-value-1	ρ value-2 Vigo Heart sensor	P- value-2
P-wave	0.86	0.01	1.00	0.01
PR-interval	0.86	0.01	1.00	0.01
QRS-complex	0.87	0.01	1.00	0.01
RR-interval	0.90	0.01	1.00	0.01
QT-interval	0.86	0.01	1.00	0.01
ST-Segment	0.86	0.01	1.00	0.01
T-wave	0.84	0.01	1.00	0.01

ρ (rho): Spearman correlation coefficient

No adverse events were recorded during the study period.

Figure 6: Scatter plots of HR, PR, RR, Temperature SBP and DBP MVM vs CE marked Standard Device methods.

Fig 7: Scattered plots of ECG parameter

4. Discussion:

The monitoring of the vitals depends on the patient condition, comorbid conditions, medical, surgical history and drugs used etc(11). The periodicity of monitoring depends on pathophysiological conditions of the patient. However, in general hospital practice it is intermittent in low acuity patient monitoring like in wards and continuous or frequent in high dependency units like ICUs(12).

The Vigo Vitals solution tested on 17 healthy volunteers and validated against the standard CE Marked devices used in clinical practice.

Live ECG and EWS Scoring: The Live ECG helps the physician to forecast the heart related abnormalities of the patient in line with other parameters. The real time ECG-Analysis and representation of the ECG-strips with events is one of the unique assets in this solution compared to the existing monitoring technologies(3). The Early Warning Scoring system helps in identifying the deterioration of the patient vitals and the same is available at different interfaces such as Bed side monitor, Nursing Station and Doctor Mobile Application. Multiple interfaces assure the ease

of data availability to the physician and monitoring nurse which will be very helpful in alerting the doctor and staying ahead of the disease(13,14).

Communication: The Bluetooth communication of devices with the Bedside Monitor helps in guaranteed data flow into the Vigo Scanea platform(15). The system works on mobile network and Wi-Fi both by which the data can be sent to cloud easily(15). Chest Biosensor is having inbuilt memory for a period of 24 hours that facilitate to retrieve the data after the monitoring period even in case any internet issues.

Monitoring: The nursing station which is a primary patient monitoring station has multiple features which are advantageous to nurse. The historical vital signs act as evidence for the patient continuous vital signs performance over a period(7,16). The vital graphs information can be useful to determine the patient stay in the facility or even to decide the patient treatment plan(17). The customization of local alert settings provides the freedom from false positives. The One-Way text communication between nurse to doctor through nursing station and doctor application negates the delay or miscommunication of the patient health status communication in case of emergencies(18). The manual errors will be reduced to minimum through automatic digital data acquisition(11,19). The physical strain of the nurse will be reduced to minimum because the nurse need not to visit the patient regularly to take vitals. The download and printable reports with automatic patient vital chart graphs reduce the nurse efforts in documentation and can compile in the case sheets directly(20).

The doctor interface app of the MVM-Vigo Vitals provides historical and live data at fingertips to the physician which helps in predicting the deterioration well ahead of the disease(21).

Digital Literacy and adoptability: The solution is designed in such a way that even a person with minimum knowledge on mobile phone or computers can onboard the patient(22). The user screens on the BSM guide the staff for smooth onboarding. As per the internal validation the adoptability of nurse to the system is 10 mins after the initial training.

Acceptancy and cooperation: The remote continuous vitals monitoring of a patient is new concept in India. However, it is gaining more importance in treatment planning(12). Since these devices are small, portable, and wireless the volunteers accepted the technology and no dropouts during the monitoring period 24 hours. The solution has achieved 100% acceptancy for its ambulatory nature during the research and no adverse reactions reported.

Economics: Multiple Vital parameters measurement data acts as an evidence tool for determining the patient stay in the hospital, hence treatment expenditure can be reduced which is one of the most important parameter to consider in Indian health care setup(18). The devices are reusable and rechargeable and no CapEx cost will be laid on the hospital since it is SaaS (Software as a Service) Model. However, the IoT cloud platform has to run continuously, and AI should analyze the data which contributes the price. A Working model must be derived for full scale implementation of the technology.

False positives: The IoT and AI-DNN model Engine works on the principle of relearning method. The DNN-AI engine used for vitals is well trained, FDA approved engine with 97.3% accuracy.

Education and Decentralized Trails: The readily available electronic data is very much useful for the retrospective analysis for research purposes. The physician can use the data to train the budding healthcare professional and doctors or nursing staff in academic settings(23). The solution becomes a handy tool for decentralized clinical trials and hence boost the future clinical research activities(9,24).

5. Conclusion:

The proposed Remote patient Multivital monitoring technology has proved its efficacy and safety in remote patient monitoring with no adverse reactions occurred since it is noninvasive device agnostic platform solution. The results on the 17 healthy volunteers found to be having high correlation and statistically significant P Value 0.001 for all the vitals compared to CE Marked devices used in medical practices. The Vitals solution developed through this research solution which consist of multiple hard assets (Devices) and soft assets (Monitoring interfaces, Analysis Platform could be perfect make for a better remote patient monitoring technology. High correlations among the vital signs between both the models are encouraging to push the developed and validated solution vigo vitals into hospital settings.

Remote health technologies have the potential to provide reliable clinical diagnosis by collecting physiological health data over a long period of time and reduce hospitalization expenditure for vulnerable patient by making it possible to monitor for critical health condition even at home. Furthermore, they open the doors for personalized healthcare and medicine by enabling deeper understanding of an individual patient physiological state and daily activities.

6. Study limitations:

Less sample number and conducted in healthy volunteer population. The Vigo Vitals solution has to prove its efficacy, accuracy in patient populations.

7. Future Scope:

The Remote Multi vital monitoring system can be integrated to hospital medical record (EMR) software and should be developed for complete at homecare monitoring solution.

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10. Conflict of interest:

MK, SP belongs to Vigo care Pvt. Ltd. These authors were not involved in data collection, analysis, and evaluation. The study was independently conducted at ESIC MCH site with no involvement of them. MAM, RKB, SB do not have conflict of interest to declare.

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